

A new complex combination of Bi^{III} utilized as a stationary phase in gas chromatography

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A new complex combination of Bi^{III} with complex anions of Cr^{III} was synthesized. It was established the structure of the combination [Bi(Rod)₃][Cr(SCN)₄(xylidin)₂]₃. This combination was utilized as a stationary phase in the separation of esters, ketones, *n*-alkanes and aromatic hydrocarbons.

Bismuth is used to prepare alloys with low melting points, to manufacture photocathodes, also as a heat carrier in nuclear technology and as gastro-intestinal dressing in the pharmaceutical industry. Taking into consideration the special properties of bismuth, it is understandable that now-a-days there is a serious investigation regarding the discovery of new methods or of new reagents that should lead to faster and more accurate determinations of bismuth¹.

Some complex compounds' capacity of including in their crystalline network molecules, with various dimensions and shapes, gave the opportunity for their use as selective stationary phases in chromatography.

Chromatographic performances were obtained through the utilization of inclusion compounds of Werner type, of cyclodextrines, of urea and thiourea².

Blokhina *et al.*³ have studied thermodynamic adsorption processes of *n*-alkanes and alcohols by using the complex combinations of nickel with Schiff bases.

Appreciable results were obtained in the aromatic hydrocarbons retention in the chromatographic gas column by making use of complex combination of cobalt⁴.

In this paper we present the synthesis and analysis of the complex combination [Bi(Rod)₃][Cr(SCN)₄(xylidin)₂]₃ as well as its utilization as stationary phase in gas chromatography.

Results and discussion

The complex combination [Bi(Rod)₃][Cr(SCN)₄(xylidin)₂]₃ was obtained starting from the reagent K₃[Cr(SCN)₆].3H₂O and the complex cation [Bi(Rod)₃]³⁺. The elemental, IR spectral and TG, ATG, DTG analyses were made.

The curves of differential thermal analyses TG and DTA

shown in Fig. 1, show a thermal stability in the temperature range of 30–150°. Decomposition begins at 180° and ends at 650°, with complete burning of the substance. The curve DTA indicates a first endothermic effect at the temperature of 150° that corresponds to a structural modification. At the temperature of 180° there appears a quite strong endothermic effect that indicates the decomposition of the complex this can be also observed on the loss curve of mass TG. This effect is strong up to the temperature of 450° when the whole quantity of substance is lost, the respective metallic oxides being obtained eventually.

The IR spectral studies of the complex anion⁵ [Cr(SCN)₆]³⁻ showed that the vibration frequency, ν_{C-N} , of the grouping NCS is situated at 2110–2140 cm⁻¹, while the vibration frequency, ν_{C-N} , at 760–810 cm⁻¹ proves the covalent character of the bond Cr^{III}-NCS. The bond between Cr^{III} and NCS is made by means of the nitrogen atom and not by sulphur⁶.

The maximum intensity of absorption situated at the vibration frequency of 2081 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the grouping NCS. The data mentioned in the literature⁷ confirm that the coordination effect has an insignificant influence upon the sequence of the complexes of type NH₄[Cr(SCN)₄(amine)₂]. The bands ν_{C-N} and ν_{C-S} do not move if in the interior sphere of coordination there are aliphatic or aromatic amines. For the xylidin combination, in the interior sphere of coordination, the vibration frequencies of valence N-H are found at 3204 cm⁻¹ (compared to uncoordinated free amines the movement is insignificant), thing which confirms that the bond Cr-N (with amines) has a strong covalent character.

The IR spectrum of the combination is rendered in Fig. 2.

The complex combination [Bi(Rod)₃][Cr(SCN)₄-

Fig. 1. The thermogravimetric and derivatographic analysis of the complex.

(xylidin)₂]₃ was used as a stationary phase in the separation of esters, ketones, *n*-alkanes and aromatic hydrocarbons.

The chromatograms obtained are presented in Figs. 3, 4

and 5.

Specific retention volumes (V_g^0) and activity coefficients at infinite dilution (γ^∞) have been determined for esters, methyl ketones and aromatic hydrocarbons (Table 1). The

Fig. 2. The IR spectrum of the complex $[\text{Bi}(\text{Rod})_3][\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_4(\text{xylidin})_2]_3$.

Fig. 3. The chromatogram of a mixture of ketones on a column having as stationary phase $[\text{Bi}(\text{Rod})_3][\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_4(\text{xylidin})_2]_3$, at a temperature of 40° : (1) ketone, (2) 2-butanone, (3) 2-pentanone, (4) *n*-butyl acetate.

Fig. 5. The chromatogram of a mixture of benzene, *m*-xylene, *o*-xylene: (1) benzene, (2) *m*-xylene, (3) *o*-xylene.

Fig. 4. The chromatogram of a mixture of esters: (1) methyl acetate, (2) ethyl acetate, (3) *i*-butyl acetate, (4) *n*-butyl acetate.

Table 1. Retention times t'_R , saturation vapor pressure p^0 , specific retention volumes V_g^0 , activity coefficients γ^∞ for some compounds at 40° . Column 5% $[\text{Bi}(\text{Rod})_3][\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_4(\text{xylidin})_2]_3$ on Chemosorb WAW, 60–80 mesh

Compd.	t'_R	p^0	V_g^0	γ^∞
Methyl acetate	1	405.572	83.230	0.230
Ethyl acetate	1.21	190.797	100.708	0.405
<i>s</i> -Butyl acetate	2.33		193.926	
<i>i</i> -Butyl acetate	2.79	38.468	233.212	0.871
<i>n</i> -Butyl acetate	3.72	26.293	309.615	0.955
Benzene	1.19	182.774	99.044	0.430
<i>m</i> -Xylene	4.17	18.931	347.069	1.184
<i>o</i> -Xylene	5.05	15.346	420.311	1.206
<i>p</i> -Xylene	4.17	19.848	347.069	1.129
Acetone	1.13	421.722	94.050	0.196
Methyl-ethyl acetone	1.51	182.122	125.677	0.340
2-Pentanone	2.44	74.301	203.081	0.515
2-Hexanone	3.53	43.770	293.802	0.600
<i>n</i> -Hexane	1.03	279.689	85.727	0.324
<i>n</i> -Heptane	1.35	92.732	112.360	0.746
<i>n</i> -Octane	2.76	31.107	229.710	1.088
<i>n</i> -Nonane	7.32	10.548	609.243	1.210

specific retention volumes were computed using the classical expression developed by Littlewood *et al.*⁸.

The solute activity coefficient at infinite dilution is uncorrected for nonideality in the vapor phase.

In Table 1 it was noticed that the values of the activity coefficient are less than 1 (negative deviation from Raoult law) or near to 1 (ideal solution), which is attributed both to the high polarizability of the complex and to the high molar volume.

At this phase, *o*-xylene separates from *m*-xylene and *s*-butyl acetate separates from *n*-butyl acetate. The alcohols were highly retained due to the hydrogen bonds formed with rhodanine.

Experimental

$\text{K}_3[\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared as described by

Brauer⁹. For the synthesis of the complex cation [Bi(Rod)₃]³⁺, we used 1.72 mg Bi^{III} and a hydroalcoholic solution 3% rhodanine (2-tio-tiazolil-4-one) in excess was added over. A yellow soluble complex¹⁰ was obtained. The sample precipitated with complex anions of Cr^{III} in concentration 3% hydroalcoholic solution. The combination K₃[Cr(SCN)₄(xylidin)₂] was obtained through a substitution reaction between K₃[Cr(SCN)₆] anhydrous and melted xylidine¹¹.

The derivatographic study was made by means of a derivatograph MOM. The measurements were made with a heating speed of 10°/min, in air atmosphere, using a platinum melting pot and samples of 100 mg.

The IR spectrum of the complex was registered in Perkin-Elmer 1600 spectrophotometer.

For the utilization of the complex as a stationary phase in gas chromatography a 5% complex on the Chromosorb WAW, 60–80 mesh was deposited.

The dimensions of the column were 3 m × 2 mm I.D. The column was conditioned for 8 h at 200°. We worked on a gas chromatograph FISONs, equipped with a detector of flame ionisation. The idle period (dead point) was determined using the homologous series of methyl-ketones.

Work conditions : column temperature – 40°; detector temperature – 180°; injector temperature – 180°; carrier gas

flow rate – 10.71 mL min⁻¹; stationary phase quantity introduced in the column – 0.1020 g; quantity of injected sample – 2µL.

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